
AUGUST 2020

**S2S (SCIENCE TO SCIENCE)
& S2B (SCIENCE TO
BUSINESS)
EXPLOITATION PLANS AND
IPR CONSORTIUM
GUIDELINES STRUCTURED**

Solar Energy for a Circular Economy

Deliverable D2.2

S2S (Science to Science) & S2B (Science to Business) Exploitation plans and IPR consortium guidelines structured

Lead Beneficiary	JM
Delivery date	16.12.2019, revision 12.08.2020
Dissemination level	Public
Version	2.0

This Project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 816336

Document Information

Grant Agreement Number	816336
Acronym	SUNRISE
Start date of project (Duration)	01/03/2019 (12 months)
Document due date	31.08.2019, revision 12.08.2020
Submission date	12.08.2020
Authors	R. Potter, P. Ellis

Deliverable number	2.2
Deliverable name	S2S (Science to Science) & S2B (Science to Business) Exploitation plans and IPR consortium guidelines structured
WP	2

Version	Date	Author	Description
v 0.1	150719	R. Potter	Creation
v 0.2	121119	P.R. Ellis	Revision
v 0.2	211119	Y. Wich/ H. Bercegol	Add-ons and comments
v 0.3	261119	P.R. Ellis	Revision
V0.3	041219	A. Roth/H.J.M. de Groot	Corrections
v1.0	081219	P.R. Ellis	Executive summary, updating, final editing
v2.0	110820	P.R. Ellis	Updating, Conclusions.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This Deliverable Report considers Intellectual Property (IP) structures and Exploitation Methods within the Sunrise partnership. A clear and efficient management system for IP is critical for the successful commercialisation and implementation of inventions within Sunrise, and hence is one of the keys to the project having impact on the energy transition. At Project level, the proposed IP system is based on current practice in collaborative projects such as Horizon 2020, where partners share background IP when relevant, and arising IP is owned by the inventing party with licences granted to other parties. Sharing of IP across the Sunrise partnership is seen to be desirable, but the mechanism for this is not yet defined. The challenge to be overcome is to allow IP sharing between projects, but without deterring commercial parties from participating due to loss of control over IP they generate.

Two forms of Exploitation are envisaged: Science-to-Science (S2S) and Science-to-Business (S2B). The mechanisms of Exploitation are different at different Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs) due to a number of factors such as the lack of clear vision as to whether the IP will be valuable (at lower TRLs) and the need for demonstrators at scale (for higher TRLs). S2S exploitation will be based on efficient communication between scientific partners (such as *via* conferences and publications) whilst S2B exploitation is founded on the early engagement and exploitation of commercial partners who might implement technology at a later date.

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1. Introduction

Execution of the Sunrise blueprint for a circular economy will bring together a diverse range of participants from academia, research organisations, society and industry. As with any multi-partner consortium, there will be a need to balance individual partner needs with overall project objectives, and over the years various forms of Legal Agreements have been constructed to deal with intellectual property matters in such situations. Although Agreements vary in detail, there are basic ground-rules that have served well in the process of handling information flow and partner expectations. It is the purpose of this deliverable to outline those ground-rules within a general guideline structure that partners can adopt for their own particular requirements. The deliverable also describes basic considerations about the exploitation of results generated in an open innovation environment, with a focus on exploiting scientific results with other scientists (Science-to-Science) and to develop commercialisable materials, devices and processes (Science-to-Business).

2. Basic IPR governance structures

All projects require an over-arching governance structure and any Legal Agreement in a partnership will need to reflect this. We recommend a similar governance structure for IP whereby all partners have a representative on an ‘IP Management Committee’ (IPMC) that should oversee the processes of publishing, patenting, managing the flow of technical and scientific information into and out of the partnership, reviewing the IP landscape relevant to the project objectives and dealing with any disputes. The IPMC should contribute to any regular reviews within the project.

It is very important that from the outset that there is clarity in respect of the rules of engagement that partners will be expected to abide by. This will facilitate both scientific information flow and the translation of acquired knowledge into practical, commercially viable technology. In particular, where there are potential conflicts of interest, such as the academic imperative to publish against the need to protect know-how that might lead to commercial exploitation, ground-rules must be in place to help resolve potential issues at an early stage. Good note taking at meetings is a ‘must’ so that correct attribution in respect of inventorship of an idea, problem-solving etc, is recorded and made transparent. Finally, a word of caution in that trust between partners, critical to a successful project, can be quickly eroded unless potential disputes are dealt with in a timely and effective manner. Being alert to signs of discontent as well as potentially patentable results will be amongst the key functions of the IPMC.

3. Typical IP Agreement layout

We provide for reference the layout of a typical IP Agreement suitable for multiple partner projects. Any Agreement should give provisions for the ownership, transfer, protection, use and dissemination of results, so-called “foreground”. The basic points should encompass:

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- Foreground resulting from the project is owned by the participant generating it.
- When foreground is generated jointly (i.e. where the separate parts of some result cannot be attributed to different participants), it will be jointly owned, unless the participants concerned agree on a different solution.
- Valuable foreground should be protected, especially when it is capable of industrial or commercial application, even if it is at an early technology readiness level (TRL). It is for the protecting party to determine what is valuable, considering future opportunities and the cost of writing, filing and maintaining the patent.
- Protection is not mandatory in all cases, though the decision not to protect foreground should be made in consultation with the other participants, who may wish to take ownership.
- An appropriate definition of Background IP. This needs to be carefully defined and any access rights clearly laid out. Note that this is a particularly sensitive area for industrial partners who are likely to request careful control regarding who has access and under what terms to their background IP. For Sunrise, background IP would be listed at project level whenever a new project starts.

4. IP Objectives

The objectives of a typical IPR strategy should follow general principles such as:

- Recognize at an early stage where valuable results are being generated.
- Help focus the research towards the highest priority areas.
- Ensure effective protection of IP rights
- Avoid work on research topics where the application is hindered or blocked by existing patent positions or prior art.

Knowledge of the IP landscape will need to be collated and mapped out for partners so that potentially troublesome areas e.g. where competitor activity is at a high level, can be identified and a suitable strategy can be put in place to modify planned work programmes or devise a work-around. Many industrial organisations use specialist software to analyse IP landscapes with visual tools that facilitate understanding of existing activity in the field, and where exploitable gaps may lie. Such tools can be very useful and are to be encouraged. However, the information will necessarily lag real-time as it can take several years for granted patents to appear in the public domain. Also, the choice of search terms can sometimes prove difficult to rationally construct so that useful information is either missed or buried in excessive ‘noise’ from irrelevant items.

In the context of Sunrise, IP issues generally occur at the project level, between parties who are engaged to co-operate. It is desirable to create interactions between the projects within Sunrise, but this leads to difficulties for commercial parties who then would be discouraged from participating. For example, a company participating in a project within Sunrise would not want to share IP with a competitor who is participating in a project which also falls under the Sunrise umbrella but is otherwise unrelated. One possible route forward would be for parties to offer suitable licenses to other projects within Sunrise. There could be a role for the consortium in facilitating this process,

maybe through creating contacts between projects or by setting out a standard template for the licenses. Overall, wider sharing of the IP which arises within Sunrise across the consortium is desirable, but it needs to be managed in a way which is acceptable to all partners, and does not discourage the participation of all kinds of businesses.

5. Effective Exploitation of the Results

One of the principal reasons for failure of technology commercialization ventures is related to a failure to understand the market properly. Accordingly, each Partnership project will need to conduct an analysis of the market needs related to the commercial use of the technology in question. For Sunrise and its intended technology goals dictated by the roadmap, most of the initial challenges are likely to relate to early TRLs such as proof of principle for a novel CO₂ reduction process or an improved catalyst for nitrogen reduction. Consequently, there may be little prospect of commercializing inventions beyond niche-type applications in the early stages.

In particular, where the intended exploitation relates to the displacement of fossil-fuel based commodity chemicals, it will be, at least initially, extremely difficult to compete on price unless there is a corresponding national or regional fiscal policy that essentially subsidizes ‘green’ products or, correspondingly, penalizes green-house gas release to provide a level playing field, as current pricing of fuels is economically complex and regulated with taxation (VAT) at the end of the value chain to finance discounts at the source to stimulate economic activity and efficiency. It follows therefore, that as part of the market analysis, due diligence must be done on understanding the existing and projected pricing, discounting and taxation frameworks across European and other economies.

Attention should also be paid to the likely supply-chain requirements for developing a particular technology. This should cover everything from raw-materials supply to end-of-life disposal. Scale-up issues should also be under scrutiny as although the technology development sequence should run as performance, then reliability, then cost, early identification of cost-effective, scalable ways of making key materials or components, will pay dividends. Indeed, where it is envisaged to exploit the technology by linking into an existing industrial process – for example by blending green hydrogen into natural gas feeds – then a good knowledge of the end-user specification such as tolerance of impurities, reliability and quantities of supply, will be essential.

As already introduced with the idea of “Sunrise Valleys” in report D2.1, full open innovation is envisaged within the individual projects of the Sunrise initiative, with full disclosure and a strong interaction between the partners in order to achieve the greatest progress. This is naturally easier at lower TRLs where individual partners have less at stake (have spent less on IP, have smaller-scale facilities etc.) than at higher TRLs where there can be significant business risk, for example in building a demonstrator facility (Figure 1).

Fig. 1. Relationship between the number of projects and the individual project cost.

6. Innovation Protocols

Different strategies for innovation are needed at different stages of a project's life, from conception through to commercialisation. The different approaches can be categorised by the different project TRLs:

Low TRLs

Low TRL working is characterised by triggering new studies and ideas and evaluating novel concepts. It's important to be able to assess whether a concept offers any chance of success quickly and efficiently in order to avoid wasting time and resources. However, it's equally important to generate basic scientific work where fundamental barriers persist and not to terminate projects without a clear understanding of why they are being stopped. One successful approach is to identify the biggest obstacle to a project's success based on evaluations at regular time intervals, and work for a limited time under reservation and close monitoring to either overcome the obstacle or stop the project. Alternative approaches to problems can often be conceived whilst working on a project, and so a stopped project can give way to a new, improved approach. The value of collaboration in low TRL activities is in the contribution to innovation. Often, partners with different backgrounds will regard the problem in different ways which allows superior solutions to be found.

Mid TRLs

Working in the middle TRLs is moving the project from the lab through a range of increasingly realistic demonstrators. The approach here is quite different to low TRL working and can involve different partners. The key issues are often in the robustness of the proposed process or material, and formulation can be important, for example in converting powders to electrodes or cells. In the mid-TRL range, an iterative approach is often used alongside improving understanding. Materials or systems characterisation can often be important. The partners involved at this stage will typically be a blend of those involved in the lower TRL work with new partners who can manufacture components at the scale needed for testing. Also important at this stage is understanding the complete system using tools such as life-cycle assessment and techno-economic analysis. These tools allow the project to be directed in beneficial directions before it is too mature for changes to be made.

High TRLs

A high TRL project is the final step before commercialisation. Here the investment costs are highest; often new facilities need to be built or existing facilities adapted to allow the project to take place. The objective is usually to demonstrate a process or material to allow investment to take place. Demonstration of a project for a significant period of time (e.g. 6 months) lowers the risk and so can be pivotal in achieving a successful project. Again, the mix of partners will have changed significantly from the lower TRL parts of the project, with emphasis on collaborators who can manufacture components at scale, and who have the facilities and access to feedstock to host the actual demonstration.

7. Exploitation Strategies

The Sunrise Roadmap envisages activities across the TRL scale from fundamental research to demonstration activities between the present time (2019) and 2050. Some of the technologies are already demonstrated (e.g. water electrolysis) whilst others are at much lower TRL such as direct electrochemical ammonia synthesis. Development of successful commercialized systems is going to require the skills and expertise of a range of actors all working together to achieve the best systems.

Considering the above, it is appropriate to consider separate strategies for exploiting science with other scientists to create better science in the future, and exploiting science to develop commercialisable materials, devices and processes. These are the science-to-science (S2S) and science to business (S2B) exploitation plans respectively. It is key to transfer meaningfully both to scientists and to businesses in order to generate impactful products in the short, medium and long terms and so to meet economic, climate and other policy goals.

Science to Science (S2S)

The main impact of S2S exploitation will be at low and mid TRLs through development of the science produced within Sunrise by scientists outside the consortium. The benefit of this is a broader fundamental understanding of relevant areas and will lead to the development of improved processes and materials in the future. Even if the TRLs of the work are low, the impact is still expected to be high, for example through the development of new materials for important applications, or in fundamentally understanding a relevant concept or phenomenon.

To engage a broad community towards the blueprint goals, scientific results relevant to progress along the multiple paths of the roadmap must be disseminated. Scientists are generally aware of the results in their field. What needs to be communicated are the specific milestones that have been reached and the remaining bottlenecks which will have to be overcome in order to fulfill the objectives. Since SUNRISE will develop its research in a wider environment, in Europe and worldwide, new important publications external to SUNRISE will also be scrutinized, and disseminated to a large community.

This dissemination plan shall include regular oral communications at scientific conferences both within and external to Sunrise. Also, special web conferences, and open discussions webinars shall be organized to increase the awareness of scientists concerning S&T barriers on the SUNRISE roadmap. One possibility is to have a dedicated team take care of following the advances on multiple fronts, then report and disseminate.

Science to Business (S2B)

The transfer of science to business is also important because it will lead to better processes and materials in the short-to-medium term. The role of science is important at the low TRL stage of a project lifetime where innovation is taking place to determine the best solution. It is also important at the mid-TRL stage where fundamental understanding is required to help make better devices and to understand and resolve degradation problems.

To gain the maximum impact from Sunrise’s scientific output, it is important to engage the business community and to create structures where businesses can be involved. Key issues such as IP need to be managed in a way which is appropriate for both commercial and academic partners and recognizes the early-stage input of research institutes and academic groups appropriately. It is important to acknowledge that there is no one-size-fits-all approach for businesses, whose needs will vary depending on size, market sector and the business model they are using. Early buy-in of commercial organisations is also important to secure funding for later, larger scale, projects. It is worth remembering that every commercial organisation will have its own identity and priorities and a one-size-fits-all approach is unlikely to be successful. Only through good understanding of these priorities can meaningful relationships be developed.

There are a number of vehicles for S2B interactions, and selecting the correct one for a project can make a significant improvement to the chances of success. For example, working at low TRLs a short proof-of-concept project might be the most appropriate, rather than initiating a Ph.D. project which might not yield results for a number of years. However, for a competency-building activity, a Ph.D. might be the perfect mechanism since it offers regular interactions over a long period of time and the opportunity to build a knowledge base.

There are a number of successful approaches to product development, such as the pipeline shown in Fig. 2. Here, the process starts with idea generation and evaluation. Between each stage there is an evaluation stage, to check whether the idea or project is on track. Key questions are asked, such as whether customers are interested, what the IP implications are, health and safety issues and so on. The questions become more detailed as a project moves through the pipeline. The activities evolve as the project moves through the process; from research and ideation through development and scale up to manufacturing.

Fig. 2. A pipeline model for product development

The advantages of a pipeline approach are in visibility and in sign-off: the stage-gate reviews between each section involve inputs from a range of disciplines such as EHS, operations and commercial teams. Projects which don’t pass the sign-off either stay in the previous stage for further work and re-review, or are stopped.

One particular bottleneck in development can be demonstration of a technology. It is typical for a technology’s robustness to be demonstrated in the application for an extended period of time, such as six months or more. This lowers the risk associated with the project and so helps financiers support the project. Finding a host for a demonstrator project can be challenging, especially for new

processes which are not yet commercialized and where side-stream reactors on existing plants do not exist. It is reasonable to think that to achieve the ambitious goals of the Sunrise Roadmap demonstrators will need to be constructed and operated with the associated costs.

8. Conclusions & Recommendations

Working under an appropriate IPR governance structure is key to maximizing the impact of investment in technologies in the Sunrise portfolio. Specific recommendations are:

- Identification and protection of key early stage results
- Researchers will have good familiarity with the relevant IP landscape, to target IP opportunities and avoid wasting resource in unfruitful areas.
- IP managed by a committee in each project.
- Good communication across Sunrise projects to allow the most efficient exploitation of results, but not in a way which deters businesses from participating.

Innovation protocols and the role of different commercial, academic and other actors will evolve as technology moves through different TRLs. Specific recommendations are:

- Communication is key for good S2S exploitation, through channels such as journals and conferences as well as more general media. The aim is to focus effort on the remaining bottlenecks to get the fastest progress to useable technologies.
- S2B exploitation is also important to allow production of the best technological solutions, and so it is important to engage businesses from the early stages of projects. The means of engagement needs to be appropriate to the stage of technology development and for the nature of the business in question. For example, at early stages, a light-touch, low cost approach would work best, whilst at higher TRLs significant levels of commercial investment would typically be needed.

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 816336